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Some More Acid Salts of Alkali Metals with 8-Hydroxyquinoline-*N*-oxide

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Manuscript received 30 December 1981,
revised 30 October 1986, accepted 3 January 1987

SOME more acid salts of alkali metals with 8-hydroxyquinoline-*N*-oxide, $ML.HL$, where $M=Li, Na, K, Rb$ or Cs and $HL=8$ -hydroxyquinoline-*N*-oxide, are being reported. Their low molar conductivities suggest them to be light ion-pairs. The IR spectra of each indicate coordination of the alkali metal with the title ligand through oxygen atoms and confirm also the presence of hydrogen bonding between L and HL , which may be a dominant factor for their stability.

Experimental

The ligand 8-hydroxyquinoline-*N*-oxide was prepared by the reported method^{1,2}.

Neutral complexes of Li, Na and K with HL: Equimolar proportions of an alkali metal salt of HL and the ligand HL were taken in absolute ethanol. On heating with continuous stirring for ~ 15 min, the contents went into solution, forming a reddish brown solution. The solution was concentrated and cooled to yield a pale brown adduct. It was filtered, washed with absolute ethanol and dried in an electric oven at 80° .

Alkali metal salts of the ligand HL were readily obtained on refluxing equimolar proportions of the metal hydroxide and the ligand HL in 95% ethanol. The yellow salts that separated, were filtered, washed with the solvent and dried in an electric oven at 80° .

Neutral complexes of Rb and Cs with HL: The alkali metal hydroxide (0.5 g) was added to a solution of 8-hydroxyquinoline-*N*-oxide (1.5 g) in absolute ethanol (15 ml). The contents were refluxed for ~ 15 min with continuous stirring, and on cooling yielded a orange coloured precipitate. It was filtered, washed with absolute ethanol and dried at 80° in an electric oven. Infrared measurements were made in nujol in the range $4000-650\text{ cm}^{-1}$. Molar conductivities were measured in *N,N*-dimethylformamide at concentration 10^{-3} M at 23° .

Results and Discussion

The complexes were soluble in most polar solvents, and insoluble in non-polar solvents. The

additional molecule of the ligand was not removed by benzene or ether. However, studies in solution and measurements of colligative properties were hampered by the dissociation of the adducts in the common solvents in which they dissolved.

The complexes decomposed in moist air, giving brown solids of indeterminate composition; the order of stability being $Li > Na > K > Rb > Cs$. All the complexes underwent a transformation at a temperature higher than the melting point of the ligand, indicating thereby their greater stability.

Infrared spectra: The free ligand exhibited^{3,4} bands at 1320 and 820 cm^{-1} , respectively, assigned to ν_{N-O} and ν_{N-O} coupled probably with OH bending modes. The $N-O$ stretching band in the spectra of the complexes exhibited a negative shift by $15-18\text{ cm}^{-1}$, besides splitting. One of the split bands was observed at 1320 cm^{-1} , which was assigned to the $N-O$ moiety of the alkali metal salt of the ligand. The other split band appeared at lower frequency and in all probability, it seemed to be due to coordination of $N-O$ moiety of the ligand molecule acting as the secondary ligand. Obviously, these features were indicative of coordination through the $N-O$ oxygen⁴. The $N-O$ bending mode in the complexes remained almost unaffected. The disappearance of the multiple medium strong bands over a wide range $2850-1750\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and shifting of the 880 cm^{-1} band of the ligand to lower frequency by 10 cm^{-1} in the complexes, provided a conclusive proof of the coordination of the ligand HL through oxygen atom of the hydroxyl moiety. A new broad band of weak to medium intensity in the region $2400-1800\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (except in case of the neutral complex of rubidium in which two such bands, the one at $2400-2300\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and the other at $1900-1800\text{ cm}^{-1}$ were observed) in all these complexes were attributed to $O-H\dots O$ absorption. This suggested the hydrogen bonding to be an essential feature of these complexes.

Conductivity: Fairly low values of molar conductivities of lithium, sodium and potassium salts of 8-hydroxyquinoline-*N*-oxide suggested light ion-pair formation; the order of the molar conductivities of these salts being $Li < Na < K$. Molar conductivities of none of these complexes approached the ideal value or 1:1 electrolyte. However, significantly low molar conductivities were indicative of covalent nature of the neutral complexes (except the sodium complex). The higher molar conductivity of $NaL.HL$ was probably due to its dissociation in solution.

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Metal Complexes as Ligands. Tri-nuclear Alkali Metal Complexes with Nickel(II)- and Palladium(II)-bisdimethylglyoximates

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Manuscript received 15 September 1984, revised 7 October 1986,
accepted 13 November 1986

TO extend the studies on 'metal complexes as ligands', we have selected Ni²⁺ and Pd²⁺ bisdimethylglyoximates as the ligands. In this paper, an attempt has been made to synthesise and characterise hetero-trinuclear alkali metal complexes derived from alkali metal salts of 8-hydroxyquinoline, 1-nitroso-2-naphthol with Ni²⁺ and Pd²⁺ bisdimethylglyoximate denoted by Ni(DMGH)₂ and Pd(DMGH)₂, respectively.

Experimental

Synthesis of the adducts: A number of stable trinuclear adducts of alkali metal salts of 1-nitroso-2-naphthol (1N2N) and 8-hydroxyquinoline

(8HQ) with Ni(DMGH)₂ and Pd(DMGH)₂ of the general formula [M_a(DMGH)₂(M_bL)₂], where M_a=Ni²⁺, Pd²⁺ and M_bL=Li, Na or K, 1-nitroso-2-naphthol or 8-hydroxyquinolines, were synthesised as the case may be. (i) The usual method of synthesis was to take Ni(DMGH)₂ or Pd(DMGH)₂ in absolute ethanol, and alkali metal salts were added to it in 1:2 molar ratio. The mixtures was refluxed on a hot-plate for 3-4 h with constant stirring, and the adducts were precipitated in hot condition. (ii) To a suspension of Ni(DMGH)₂ in absolute ethanol, one or two pellets of NaOH were added avoiding excess, and the whole mixture was stirred for 15 min. The red colour of Ni(DMGH)₂ changed to dark yellow and part of the product went into solution. The resulting disodium-bisdimethylglyoximates-Ni²⁺, Na₂[Ni(DMG)₂] was treated with 1N2N/8HQ in absolute ethanol. The brownish red/pale green compounds that formed, were washed with ethanol and dried at 80°. The corresponding lithium and potassium complexes of Ni(DMGH)₂, and all the alkali metal adducts with Pd(DMGH)₂ were synthesised by the same method.

Analytical data, decomposition temperature and relevant ir bands are presented in Tables 1 and 2.

The colours of the adducts [M_a(DMGH)₂(M_bL)₂] are different from those of the complex ligands [M_a(DMGH)₂]. The higher decomposition temperatures of these adducts compared to those of M(DMGH)₂, showed the strong bonding, most likely through oxygen atoms of the 'complex ligand' to the alkali metals. These compounds are stable under anhydrous condition but decompose on

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF THE ADDUCTS M_a(DMGH)₂(M_bL)₂

Compd.*	Colour	Decomp. temp.	Analysis %: Found/(Calcd.)		
			N	Ni/Pd	Na/K
(Li1N2N) ₂ .X	Brown	285	12.3 (13.0)	9.4 (9.0)	-
(Na1N2N) ₂ .X	Brown	275	12.4 (11.7)	9.9 (8.6)	6.9 (6.4)
(K1N2N) ₂ .X	Brownish yellow	270	11.3 (11.8)	8.0 (8.1)	10.00 (11.01)
(Li8HQ) ₂ .X	Green	245	13.7 (14.2)	9.3 (9.8)	-
(Na8HQ) ₂ .X	Green	242	12.95 (13.50)	9.8 (9.3)	7.1 (7.4)
(K8HQ) ₂ .X	Green	230	11.9 (12.7)	9.20 (8.89)	10.8 (11.9)
(Li1N2N) ₂ .Y	Brown	290	12.7 (13.2)	15.8 (16.1)	-
(Na1N2N) ₂ .Y	Brownish grey	282	11.1 (11.5)	12.6 (13.2)	5.9 (6.3)
(K1N2N) ₂ .Y	Brownish black	280	12.0 (11.1)	13.2 (14.0)	9.6 (10.3)
(Li8HQ) ₂ .Y	Yellowish green	300	12.72 (13.20)	17.2 (16.6)	-
(Na8HQ) ₂ .Y	Greenish yellow	295	11.9 (12.5)	14.90 (15.86)	6.40 (6.88)
(K8HQ) ₂ .Y	Greenish yellow	288	11.1 (12.0)	14.0 (15.1)	10.8 (11.1)

*X = Ni(DMGH)₂, Y = Pd(DMGH)₂.